

Synthesis of some 3-Aroyl-4-alkylbenzopyran-1*H*-1-ones and Mechanistic Studies on the Synthesis of 3-Aroyl-4-arylbenzopyran-1*H*-1-ones^ψ

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Reactions of bromoacetophenones (2) with *o*-acyl/aroylbenzoic acids (1,4) yielded the products 4-alkyl-3-aryolbenzopyran-1*H*-1-ones (3) and 3-aryolbenzofuran-1*H*-1-ones (6). The high product selectivity is observed depending upon the nature of the substrate taken.

Benzopyran-1*H*-1-ones (isocoumarins) are a class of naturally occurring lactones that display a wide range of biological activity¹. The synthesis of this nucleus with and without any substitution has been the object of research for over hundred years. There are diverse approaches towards the syntheses of mono- and 3,4-disubstituted isocoumarins using classical² as well as transition metal mediated³ organic synthetic methodologies. Although these methods are potentially quite versatile, a review reveals that only very few methods are known for the synthesis of aroyl substituted isocoumarins particularly at 3- or 4-position. Masaya and Masayasu⁴ synthesized 4-aryolisocoumarins and established their antiallergic property. Here, we describe a simple and general approach towards 4-alkyl/aryl-3-aryolisocoumarins using readily available starting materials.

Results and Discussion

Treatment of *o*-acylbenzoic acids (1) with bromoacetophenone (2) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in ethyl methyl ketone furnished different 3-aryol-4-alkylisocoumarins (3) (Scheme 1). No side-product was detected from the reaction mixture. Similar result was obtained when 1 was condensed with bromoacetylnaphthalene (2e) (Scheme 1).

Success of this synthesis encouraged us to apply this methodology to the synthesis of 3-aryol-4-aryl derivatives (Scheme 2). The first acid used was *o*-(3',4'-dimethylbenzoyl)benzoic acid (4a). It was very surprising that we failed to isolate the expected 3-aryol-4-arylisocoumarin (5). A mixture of two compounds were formed (from tlc). The separation of the crude reaction mixtures led to the isolation of 3-substituted-benzofuran-1*H*-1-one (phthalide) (6a) and phenylglyoxal (7a).

The key information to identify the product as phthalide and not isocoumarin are provided by ir, nmr, mass spectra as well as elemental analysis. The ir band at ~1740 cm⁻¹ (C=O) suggests the presence of five-membered lactone ring. The compound 5 would have exhibited two carbonyl peaks, the one for benzylic ketone and the other for six-membered lactone ring. In ¹H nmr spectra of 6a, the benzylic proton signal appears at δ 6.2 as one proton singlet, which again supports the formation of 6a and not 5. Final-

ly, the possibility of formation of isocoumarin derivative is eliminated from mass spectral analysis. There is no peak beyond *m/z* 239 whereas theoretically, compound 5 should give molecular ion peak at *m/z* 354 if Ar' = *o*-xyloyl and Ar = phenyl. Ir and elemental analysis data suggested the second compound to be phenylglyoxal (7a). Further confirmation of formation of phenylglyoxal was done by synthesizing it from acetophenone and SeO₂ 5.

The above result indicates that during course of the reaction ring contraction takes place. To draw any firm

Scheme 1

^ψPresented in 32nd Annual Convention of Chemists, 1995.

Scheme 2

conclusion a series of *o*-aroylbenzoic acids (4b-f) were reacted with the bromo compounds (2a and e). It was found that ring contraction is independent of the nature of the bromo compounds used and is a general case for *o*-aroylbenzoic acid. Then we can say that the related bromoacetophenone (2a) which is expected to be introduced as aroyl group at 3-position of isocoumarin must undergo some structural transformation which is reflected in the formation of two products.

Scheme 3

Based on the above observation, a mechanism may be proposed to account for the reaction (Scheme 3). In presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate, reaction of potassium salt of aromatic acid yields a species (I) which in turn forms enolate (II) in presence of base. This then reacts with electrophilic carbonyl carbon to give (III). After that the reaction follows two completely different pathways depending upon the nature of R. If R = alkyl, the intermediate (III) eliminates a molecule of water to give isocoumarin derivative (IV).

But when R = aryl, this type of dehydration seems to produce significant strain due to *cis*-orientation of two bulky groups across the double bond. Although alcohols are not particularly good nucleophiles, but due to the $-I$ effect of phenyl rings the acid character of benzylic hydroxyl group is high enough to be attacked by base to yield phthalide derivatives.

In conclusion, we may say that besides the above mentioned factors other factors might have played important role. A further investigation of this reaction is in progress.

Experimental

All reactions were performed under anhydrous conditions and methyl ethyl ketone was dried according to standard method. All m.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel. Ir spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer, ^1H nmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 instrument. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

o-Acylbenzoic acid, *o*-aroylbenzoic acids and bromo compounds (2a-f) were prepared according to reported methods.

4-Methyl-3-benzoylbenzopyran-1H-1-one (3a): A mixture of 2-bromoacetophenone (2a; 1 g, 0.005 mol), acetophenone-*o*-carboxylic acid (1; 0.8 g, 0.005 mol) and anhyd. potassium carbonate (2.0 g) in dry methyl ethyl ketone (15 ml) was refluxed for 8–10 h on a steam-bath. Solvent was then removed, water added and extracted with ether. Etheral layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of ether the crude product was crystallized from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)-methanol to give 3a (50–55%). Similar reaction conditions were employed for the preparation of 3b-e (Scheme 1). 2,4-Dinitro derivatives of 3a-e were prepared which gave satisfactory nitrogen analysis.

4-Ethyl-3-benzoylbenzopyran-1H-1-one (3f): A mixture of 2-bromoacetophenone (2a; 1 g, 0.005 mol), propiophenone-*o*-carboxylic acid (1b; 0.9 g, 0.005 mol) and anhyd. potassium carbonate (2.0 g) in dry methyl ethyl ketone (15 ml) was refluxed for 8–10 h on a steam-bath. Then the same procedure was followed as above to yield 3f. Similarly other compounds (yields 45–58%) were prepared: 3a, m.p. 133–34°, v_{max} 1670 (ketone), 1732 (lac-

tone), δ 2.44 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.53–8.02 (m, ArH), 8.47 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, Ar-8-H); m/z 264 (M⁺ 8.36%), 105 (base peak, C₆H₅CO); **b**, 178–79°; **c**, 78°; **d**, 95°, **e**, 168–69°, m/z 315 (M⁺, 17.4%), 156 (base peak due to C₁₀H₇CO, 21.9%), 127 (C₁₀H₇, 19.57%); **f**, 123–24°; **g**, 165–66°. All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses. Then the same procedure was followed as above to yield **3f**. 2,4-Dinitro derivatives of **3f-g** gave satisfactory nitrogen analysis.

3-Phenylbenzofuran-1H-1-one (6b) : A mixture of **2a** (1 g, 0.005 mol), *o*-benzoylbenzoic acid (**4b**; 1.2 g, 0.005 mol) and anhyd. potassium carbonate (2.0 g) in dry ethyl methyl ketone (15 ml) was refluxed for 10–12 h. Then solvent was removed, water added and extracted with ether. The usual workup resulted in a crude mixture containing two components (tlc). The crude product was left overnight in a mixture of petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)-methanol, and the resulting solid was washed, dried and crystallized from methanol; similarly other compounds (yields 40–50%) **6a**, m.p. 130–31°, ν_{\max} 1745 cm⁻¹ (lactone), δ 2.25 (6H, s, CH₃), 6.24 (1H, s, phthalide-H), 6.8–7.7 (m, ArH), 7.9 (d, J 8 Hz, Ar 7-H), m/z 238 (M⁺ 25.18%), 223 (M⁺-CH₃ base peak, 35.58%); **b**, 114–15°; **c**, 144–45°; **d**, 134–35°; **e**, 193–94°. All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses. From the mother liquor, phenylglyoxal (**7a**) was isolated. It gave the oxazone (m.p. 149–50°) and other satisfactory chemical tests. Formation of phenylglyoxal was finally confirmed by its synthesis following the known procedure⁵.

Similarly, compounds **6a,c-e** were prepared (Scheme 2).

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References

1. R. P. BARRY, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 229.
2. A. KAMAL, A. ROBERTSON, and E. TETTENSOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3375; J. N. CHATTERJEA, C. BHAKTA, and T. RADHAVAKULA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 1161; B. K. SARKHEL and J. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 925; R. H. CARTER, R. M. COLYER, R. A. HILL, and J. STAUNTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1976, **13**, 1438; R. P. SINGH and J. M. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B.*, 1982, **21**, 104; N. NAGARIAN and T. R. BALASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B.*, 1987, **26**, 917; 1988, **27**, 380.
3. D. E. KORTE, L. S. HEGEDEUS, and R. K. WIRTH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **42**, 1329; R. C. LAROCK, S. VARAPATH, H. H. LAU, and C. A. FELLOWS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 5274; G. BATU and R. J. STEVENSON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1980, **45**, 1532; T. SAKAMOTO, M. ANNAKA, Y. KONDO, and H. YAMANAKA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1986, **34**, 2754; T. IZUMI, Y. NISHIMOTO, K. KOHI, and A. KASHORE, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1990, **27**, 1419; N. G. KUNDU and M. PAL, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1993, 86; H-Y. LIAO and C-H. CHENG, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **60**, 3711; R. C. LAROCK, E. K. YUM, M. J. DOTY, and K. K. C. SHAM, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **60**, 3270.
4. K. MASSAYASU and K. MASAYA, *Chem., Abstr.*, 1977, **86**, 155511.
5. "Vogel's Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., E.L.B.S., p. 440.